

The Rarámuri

Secondary source

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* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Religious Group, Mesoamerican Religions, Polytheistic, Language, Uto-Aztecan, Southern Uto-Aztecan, Tarahumara-Guarjijo

The Rarámuri (also known as Tarahumara) inhabited the Sierra Madre Occidental, particularly in what is now the northern region of Chihuahua, Mexico. They were primarily agrarian, and cultivated using techniques suited to the mountainous environment. Their settlement patterns were characterized by scattered villages or rancherías, often located in difficult-to-reach areas, providing both protection and access to natural resources.

Date Range: 700 CE - 1580 CE

Region: Western Sierra Madre (The Tarahumara Mountains)

Region tags: Mexico

The Tarahumara Mountains, part of the Sierra Madre Occidental in northern Mexico, are a rugged, canyon-filled region that has historically sheltered the Rarámuri people. Their isolation has helped preserve their cultural and linguistic traditions.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Fuente 1: Montemayor, C. Los Tarahumaras: Pueblo de Estrellas y Barrancas. Mexico: Editorial Aldus, 2008
- Fuente 2: González, L. Crónicas de La Sierra Tarahumara. México: SEP, 1987
- Fuente 3: Zingg, R. Behind the Mexican Mountains. Edited by H. Campbell, J. Peterson, and D. Carmichael. United States of America: University of Texas Press, 2001

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- URL de la Fuente 1: <https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-ramuri>
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (Rarámuri)," 2017. <https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-ramuri>.
- URL de la Fuente 2: <https://atlas.inpi.gob.mx/tarahumaras-ubicacion/>
- Descripción de la Fuente 2: Instituto de los Pueblos Indígenas de Mexico, ed. "Atlas de Los Pueblos Indígenas de Mexico - Tarahumaras," 2020. <https://atlas.inpi.gob.mx/tarahumaras-ubicacion/>.
- URL de la Fuente 3: https://books.google.ca/books/about/La_sierra_tarahumara_o_los_desvelos_de_l.html?id=5Q0VAAAAYAAJ&redir_esc=y
- Descripción de la Fuente 3: Cajas Castro, J. La Sierra Tarahumara o Los Desvelos de La Modernidad En México. México: Consejo Nacional para la Cultura y las Artes, 1992

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- URL de la Fuente 1: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/261781774_Raramuri_Souls_Knowledge_and_Social_Process_in_Northern_Mexico_by_1
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: Merrill, W. L. Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.
- URL de la Fuente 2: <https://books.google.ca/books?>

id=41B4t3DqehsC&hl=es&source=gbs_book_other_versions

– Descripción de la Fuente 2: Pintado Cortina, A.P. Tarahumaras. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

– URL de la Fuente 3:

https://www.academia.edu/35779351/Gramatica_Tarahumara_de_Thomas_de_Guadalajara_1683_

– Descripción de la Fuente 3: Rodríguez López, A., ed. Gramática Tarahumara (1683): Compendio Del Arte de La Lengua de Los Tarahumares y Guazapares de Tomás de Guadalajara. Chihuahua: Universidad Autónoma de Ciudad Juárez, 2010

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Before Spanish arrival, the present-day state of Chihuahua was inhabited by several Indigenous groups, including but not limited to the Tubares, Tobosos, Cocoyomes, Joyas, Conchos, Guazapares, Chinipas, Salineros, and Pimas. The Rarámuri lived along the eastern slopes of the Sierra Tarahumara and remained isolated from the rest of the groups. There is limited information about their pre-Hispanic culture and way of life, and it is currently unknown whether they maintained culture with the other Indigenous groups in the area. (Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017)

Reference: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017.
<https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-raramuri>.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The Rarámuri religion was deeply integrated into the social and cultural structure of the community. As is the case with several other Mesoamerican groups, the Raramuri religion was deeply linked to communal life. (Rodríguez López, 2012; Pintado Cortina, 2004)

Reference: Pintado Cortina, A.P.. Tarahumaras. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Reference: Rodríguez López, A.. "Religión O Praxis Religiosa En El Mundo Indígena: El Caso Rarámuri Del Alto Río Conchos". Cuicuilco 19, no. 55 (2012): 43-68.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence that the Raramuri actively engaged in proselytism to recruit new members. They were a secluded community before the Spanish conquest and had limited contact with other groups. (Pintado Cortina, 2004; Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017)

Reference: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017.
<https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-raramuri>.

Reference: Pintado Cortina, A.P.. Tarahumaras. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Does the religion have official political support

– Sí

Notes: The religion of the Tarahumaras was present in interpersonal relationships, in the political institutions of the community, and in the moral values, norms, and customs that governed their society. (Merrill, 1988; López Austin & López Lujan, 2001; Pintado Cortina, 2004)

Reference: Pintado Cortina, A.P.. Tarahumaras. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Reference: Merrill, W. L. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

Reference: López Austin, A., and L. López Luján. *El Pasado Indígena*. México: FCE, 2001.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There is no indication of a formal concept of apostasy comparable to that found in later organized religions such as Christianity. (Pintado Cortina, 2004)

Reference: Pintado Cortina, A.P.. *Tarahumaras*. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Precise population data for the pre-Hispanic Rarámuri is unclear to this date, however, archaeological evidence indicates that their communities may have numbered in the several thousands. (Martínez Ramírez, 2020)

Reference: Martínez Ramírez, M.I. *Teoría Etnográfica: Crónica Sobre La Antropología Rarámuri*. Mexico: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2020.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The Rarámuri religion was present in interpersonal relationships, in the community core, such as moral values, norms, and customs that governed their society (Instituto de los Pueblos Indígenas de México, 2017; Martínez Ramírez, 2020).

Reference: Martínez Ramírez, M.I. *Teoría Etnográfica: Crónica Sobre La Antropología Rarámuri*. Mexico: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2020.

Reference: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017.
<https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-aramuri>.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The Raramuri did not have a sacred text or any form of sacred written language. Instead of written scriptures, religious traditions were primarily transmitted orally through stories, rituals, and ceremonies conducted by priests or community leaders. (Pintado Cortina, 2004; Rodríguez López, 2012)

Reference: Pintado Cortina, A.P.. *Tarahumaras*. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Reference: Rodríguez López, A.. "Religión O Praxis Religiosa En El Mundo Indígena: El Caso Rarámuri Del Alto Río Conchos". *Cuicuilco* 19, no. 55 (2012): 43-68.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Pre-Hispanic Rarámuri settlements consisted of dispersed residential, symbolic, and mortuary spaces integrated into the natural landscape (such as caves, fields, and ceremonial patios) without large-scale constructions. Ritual activity relied on natural features rather than built structures. (Chacón Soria, 2022)

Reference: Chacón Soria, E.. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Sí

Notes: There are records of rocks marked and decorated by owirúames (Rarámuri healers) and wa'rura (elders), with symbolic markings related to ancestral narratives transmitted across generations. (Wyndham, 2011)

Reference: Wyndham, F. S.. "The Semiotics of Powerful Places: Rock Art and Landscape Relations in the Sierra Tarahumara, Mexico.". *Journal of Anthropological Research* 67, no. 3 (2011): 387-420.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Únicamente en espacios religiosos públicos

Notes: The Rarámuri used wooden masks, drums, rustic crosses, and carved figures, often for ceremonial purposes. (Merrill, 1988)

Reference: Merrill, W. L.. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Sí

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– El campo lo desconoce

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Sí

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Sí

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Elite Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Sí

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– El campo lo desconoce

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– El campo lo desconoce

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– El campo lo desconoce

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:

– El campo lo desconoce

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Sí

Notes: Although pre-Hispanic Rarámuri iconography is not abundant, there are distinctive elements in rock art and ritual objects associated with their worldview. These include petroglyphs, cave paintings, and symbolic representations linked to natural elements (such as the sun and sacred animals), as well as specific designs on drums, masks, and ceremonial crosses. (Breen Murray, 1983)

Reference: Breen Murray, W.. "Tres Sitios De Pinturas Rupestres En La Alta Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 20, no. 1 (1983).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Sí

Notes: The concept of arewá, translated as "vital force" or "soul," refers to a non-material essence that animates and sustains life. (Pintado Cortina, 2004)

Reference: Pintado Cortina, A.P. Tarahumaras. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: According to their cosmological beliefs, there is a vertical interpretation in which three levels exist above the Earth's surface, a flat-circular plane, and three below, all encircled by a body of water. (González, 1987; Bonfiglioli, 2008)

Reference: González, L.. Crónicas De La Sierra Tarahumara. México: SEP, 1987.

Reference: Bonfiglioli, C.. "El Yúmari, Clave De Acceso a La Cosmología Rarámuri". Cuicuilco 15, no. 42 (2008): 45-60.

Reincarnation in this world:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: As mentioned by González (1987), it has been established that the "soul" travels to one of six levels. However, there is no explicit evidence of its return to the physical world in a new body.

Reference: González, L.. Crónicas De La Sierra Tarahumara. México: SEP, 1987.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Sí

Notes: Corpses were often placed lying on their back, with hands placed on their chests. (Fujigaki, 2009)

Reference: Fujigaki Lares, J. A.. La Muerte Y Sus Metáforas: Ensayo Sobre La Ritualidad Mortuoria Y Sacrificial Rarámuri En El Noroeste De México. Tesis de Maestría. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2009.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Sí (especifique): Clothes, corn, beans, personal objects.

Notes: Corpses were dressed in fine clothing, and small offerings were placed alongside it. Bodies needed to remain in light so that the soul was able to "travel unburdened". (Fujigaki, 2009)

Reference: Fujigaki Lares, J. A. *La Muerte Y Sus Metáforas: Ensayo Sobre La Ritualidad Mortuoria Y Sacrificial Rarámuri En El Noroeste De México*. Tesis de Maestría. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2009.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Sí

↳ Personal effects:

– Sí

Notes: Personal objects were often placed next to the bodies alongside small offerings. (Fujigaki, 2009)

Reference: Fujigaki Lares, J. A. *La Muerte Y Sus Metáforas: Ensayo Sobre La Ritualidad Mortuoria Y Sacrificial Rarámuri En El Noroeste De México*. Tesis de Maestría. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2009.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Valuable items:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Offerings were placed next to the bodies. It is unclear whether these objects carried something other than symbolic significance. (Chacón Soria, 2022)

Reference: Chacón Soria, E. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other grave goods:

– El campo lo desconoce

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Sí

Notes: During the Pre-Hispanic era, Rarámuri funerary customs first involved finding a cave or small rock shelter away from the dwelling, followed by performing the burial ritual and farewell to the deceased. (Chacón Soria, 2022)

Reference: Chacón Soria, E.. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest that the Rarámuri used cenotaphs in their burial practices.

↳ In cemetery:

– Sí

Notes: Recent evidence suggests that, although Raramuri didn't have formal cemeteries, they carried out formal burials inside caves (Chacón Soria, 2022).

Reference: Chacón Soria, E.. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Sí (especifique): Caves.

Notes: Archaeological studies of the Sierra Tarahumara bear witness to numerous cave burials, a practice that is also frequently recalled by the Rarámuri themselves. (Chacón Soria, 2022)

Reference: Chacón Soria, E.. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Sí

Notes: The Raramuri believed in a Pantheon of deities, including but not limited to Onorúame (Our Father), Iyeruame (Our Mother) Sukristo and Santi (sons and daughters of the divine) and natural forces like the wind, animals and peyote plant. (Lieberman et al., 2020; Bonfiglioli, 2005; Montemayor, 2008)

Reference: Lieberman, D. E., M. Mahaffey, S.C. Quimare, N.B. Holowka, I.J. Wallace, and A.L. Baggish. "Running in Tarahumara (rarámuri) Culture: Persistence Hunting, Footracing, Dancing, Work, and the Fallacy of the Athletic Savage". *Current Anthropology* 61, no. 3 (2020): 356-79.

Reference: Bonfiglioli, C.. "Jíkuri Sepawa'ame (la " Raspa De Peyote)": Una Danza De Curación En La Sierra Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 39, no. 2 (2005): 151-88.

Reference: Montemayor, C.. *Los Tarahumaras: Pueblo De Estrellas Y Barrancas*. Mexico: Editorial Aldus, 2008.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Sí

Notes: Onorúame, "Our Father," is associated with the Sun, and Tamujé Yerá or Iyerúame, "Our Mother," is associated with the Moon. (Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017)

Reference: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017.
<https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-raramuri>.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Sí

Notes: Modern religious syncretism has developed the notion of the Riablo, seen not as an absolute evil, but as an elder brother of Onorúame who sometimes assists in maintaining moral justice. It is unclear whether this deity dates back to precolumbine era. (Lieberman et al., 2020)

Reference: Lieberman, D. E., M. Mahaffey, S.C. Quimare, N.B. Holowka, I.J. Wallace, and A.L. Baggish. "Running in Tarahumara (rarámuri) Culture: Persistence Hunting, Footracing, Dancing, Work, and the Fallacy of the Athletic Savage". *Current Anthropology* 61, no. 3 (2020): 356-79.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Sí (especifique): The owirúames are the "shamans" responsible for healing and leading rituals, serving as a connection between Rarámuri society and the gods. (Bennet and Zingg, 1935)

Reference: Bennet, W.C., and R.M. Zingg. *The Tarahumara, an Indian Tribe of Northern Mexico*. Univ. Chicago Press, 1935.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: In the pre-Hispanic Rarámuri worldview, Onorúame (the supreme god) was primarily associated with creation, well-being, morality, and communal balance (in other words, human affairs) while other spirits or forces (such as animals, weather, or mountains) governed aspects of the natural and spiritual world. (Lomnitz-Adler, 1992)

Reference: Lomnitz-Adler, C.. Exits from the Labyrinth: Culture and Ideology in the Mexican National Space. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Sí

Notes: Divine favor was sought from the Gods through songs, dances, and rituals performed in open spaces.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Sí

Notes: Myths recount that, through the use of peyote, the owirúames are able to communicate with the deities in order to receive knowledge from them. (Bonfiglioli, 2005; Bonfiglioli and Gutiérrez del Ángel, 2012)

Reference: Bonfiglioli, C.. "Jíkuri Sepawa'ame (la " Raspa De Peyote)": Una Danza De Curación En La Sierra Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 39, no. 2 (2005):

151-88.

Reference: Bonfiglioli, C., and A. Gutiérrez del Ángel. "Peyote, Enfermedad Y Regeneración De La Vida Entre Huicholes Y Tarahumaras". *Cuicuilco* 19, no. 53 (2012): 196-222.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Sí

Notes: Some early twentieth century ethnographical studies have argued that Onorúame (the supreme god) had the ability to reward or punish humans based on their behavior. He could intervene through blessings (such as good harvests or health) or punishments (such as illness or misfortune) when communal norms were transgressed. (Lumholtz, 1902; Bennet and Zingg, 1935)

Reference: Lumholtz, C.. *Unknown Mexico; a Record of Five Years' Exploration Among the Tribes of the Western Sierra Madre; in the Tierra Caliente of Tepic and Jalisco; and Among the Tarascos of Michoacan*. United States : C. Scribner's sons, 1902.

Reference: Bennet, W.C., and R.M. Zingg. *The Tarahumara, an Indian Tribe of Northern Mexico*. Univ. Chicago Press, 1935.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Sí

Notes: In the Rarámuri worldview, Onorúame exerted influence over the world through the balance of human relationships, communal rituals, and moral norms. (Merrill, 1988)

Reference: Merrill, W. L.. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Sí

Notes: Onorúame is described as an emotional figure, with human-like emotions. Positive expressions included rewarding those who maintain balance, harmony, and respect for communal norms (some examples of these rewards could be granting health, rain, or abundant harvests). He also showed negative emotion by punishing behaviors that disrupt the moral or social order (illness, drought, or misfortune are some example of these). (Merrill, 1988)

Reference: Merrill, W. L.. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Sí

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Sí

Notes: In addition to Onorúame (the supreme god), other supernatural beings were venerated. These included Iyeruame (the Mother), nature spirits, and animistic forces and sacred plants such as hikuli (peyote), which was considered a powerful being with spiritual agency. (Bye, 1979; Merrill, 1988; Arrieta, 1992)

Reference: Bye, R.A.. *Ethnoecology of the Tarahumara of Chihuahua, Mexico*. United States: Harvard University Press, 1979.

Reference: Merrill, W. L.. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

Reference: Arrieta, O.. "Religion and Ritual Among the Tarahumara Indians of Northern Mexico: Maintenance of Cultural Autonomy Through Resistance and Transformation of Colonizing Symbols". *Wičazo Ša Review* 8, no. 2 (1992): 11-23.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ In dreams:

– Sí

↳ In trance possession:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Through divination practices:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Sí (especifique): Onorúame (Supreme god) communicates with the living in a symbolic and indirect way—through signs in nature, dreams, rituals, and the mediation of shamans (owiruames). (Martínez, 2010)

Reference: Martínez, I.. "Sueños Y Chamanismo Rarámuri: La Generación Y El Control Del Conflicto Social". In *Iniciaciones, Trances, Sueños. Investigaciones Sobre El Chamanismo En México*, 251-66. Mexico: Plaza y Valdés México, 2010.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Sí

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Spirits may be sensed through physical effects such as chills, illness, dizziness, or unexplained misfortune. (Merrill, 1988)
 - Reference: Merrill, W. L. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Spirits may intentionally intervene (punish or protect the living) based on moral behavior or ritual neglect. (Merrill, 1988)
 - Reference: Merrill, W. L. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Sí

- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Sí

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Spirits are believed to retain some memory of their earthly lives, particularly family, moral duties, and unresolved matters. Rituals aim to help them forget these ties and pass peacefully. (Merrill, 1988)
 - Reference: Merrill, W. L. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Spirits may offer protection, fertility, or health when honored. They may also express anger or sadness through illness or misfortune if they are dishonored, forgotten or buried improperly. (Merrill, 1988)
 - Reference: Merrill, W. L. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Sí

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Sí

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Sí

Notes: Communication occurs through dreams, signs in nature and shamanic visions. (Merrill, 1988; Martínez, 2010)

Reference: Merrill, W. L. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

Reference: Martínez, I. "Sueños Y Chamanismo Rarámuri: La Generación Y El Control Del Conflicto Social". In *Iniciaciones, Trances, Sueños. Investigaciones Sobre El Chamanismo En México*, 251-66. Mexico: Plaza y Valdés México, 2010.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Sí (especifique): Signs in nature

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: Deities, linked to natural elements such as crops and rain, are typically depicted in anthropomorphic forms.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There isn't much literature explaining how much the deities knew about humans; Scholars agree, however, that the Rarámuri believed the gods could punish or reward according to certain human actions. (Lomnitz-Adler, 1992; Merrill, 1988)

Reference: Lomnitz-Adler, C.. Exits from the Labyrinth: Culture and Ideology in the Mexican National Space. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992.

Reference: Merrill, W. L.. Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Sí

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Sí

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Both the Supreme God (Onorúame) and spirits had the ability to punish individuals who transgressed moral norms.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Sí

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Sí

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Sí

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Sí

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Illness, poor harvests, or accidents are some examples of what was interpreted as signs of moral or ritual imbalance. All these punishments occurred in this realm. (Merrill, 1988) It is unknown whether individuals who transgressed moral order also received punishment after their death.

Reference: Merrill, W. L. Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Sí

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Sí

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Sí

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Sí

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– No

↳ Done randomly:
– No

Notes: The rituals were performed to seek the favor of the gods, such as requesting rain to ensure a good harvest.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Sí

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Sí
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Sí

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Raramuri religious morality was deeply tied to communal well-being and social structures. Moral transgression was deeply tied to religious transgression. (Rodríguez López, 2012)

Reference: Rodríguez López, A. "Religión O Praxis Religiosa En El Mundo Indígena: El Caso Rarámuri Del Alto Río Conchos". Cuicuilco 19, no. 55 (2012): 43-68.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Current Rarámuri practices do include fasting as an important component of the Noríruachi (Holy week). (Acuña Delgado, 2005) It is unknown whether this practice dates back to the pre-Hispanic Rarámuri religious practices.

Reference: Acuña Delgado, É.. "Semana Santa En Norogachi: Fiesta Y Espectáculo Del Sincretismo Religioso Rarámuri". INDIANA, no. 22 (2005): 101-26.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Sí

Notes: Shamans engage in multiple practices, they could serve as healers, ritual facilitators, and custodians of cultural heritage. They may operate on a full-time or occasional basis by either fulfilling specialized functions or supporting roles alongside other ritual experts. (Zingg, 2001) Maintaining balanced reciprocity across different realms involved regular participation in community rituals and healing ceremonies. (Levi, 1999)

Reference: Zingg, R.. Behind the Mexican Mountains. Edited by H. Campbell, J. Peterson, and D. Carmichael. United States of America: University of Texas Press, 2001.

Reference: Levi, J.M.. "The Embodiment of a Working Identity: Power and Process in Rarámuri Ritual Healing". American Indian Culture and Research Journal 23, no. 3 (1999): 91-114.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Sí

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Given the diversity of ritual practices, both the duration and number of participants can vary significantly. Some rituals may be performed for the healing of an individual family member, while others may have involved collective participation aimed at securing a favorable crop (Bonfiglioli and Gutiérrez del Ángel, 2012).

Reference: Bonfiglioli, C., and A. Gutiérrez del Ángel. "Peyote, Enfermedad Y Regeneración De La Vida Entre Huicholes Y Tarahumaras". Cuicuilco 19, no. 53 (2012): 196-222.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– No

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Sí (especifique): Staffs, jicara, bowls with beverages.

Notes: Recent studies describe some current practices based on pre-Hispanic healing rituals. During these rituals, offerings are placed to the east, while the ritual specialist and the sick sit to the west (men on the left and women on the right). Central elements include the peyote leader, placed in a pit covered by a jicara; a fire kept burning through the night; and two ceremonial staffs: scraped to produce sound. (Bonfiglioli and Gutiérrez del Ángel, 2012)

Reference: Bonfiglioli, C., and A. Gutiérrez del Ángel. "Peyote, Enfermedad Y Regeneración De La Vida Entre Huicholes Y Tarahumaras". Cuicuilco 19, no. 53 (2012): 196-222.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Sí

Notes: The main deities are Támujé Onorá or Onóruame ("Our Father") associated with the Sun, and Tamujé Yerá or Iyerúame, ("Our Mother"), associated with the Moon. (Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017)

Reference: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017.
<https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-raramuri>.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Sí

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Una tribu

Notes: Bennett and Zingg's (1935) classic study labels the Rarámuri explicitly as a tribe, describing their semi-nomadic ranchería settlements and lack of centralized political power. Little is known about the Raramuri political and social structure before the Spanish arrival, although most researchers agree that they organized primarily through dispersed tribal groups, based on kinship ties, reciprocity, and communal cooperation.

Reference: Bennet, W.C., and R.M. Zingg. *The Tarahumara, an Indian Tribe of Northern Mexico*. Univ. Chicago Press, 1935.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Rarámuri religious traditions involve ceremonies intended to promote agricultural abundance and successful harvests. However, there is no evidence that these practices provided institutionalized forms of relief during times of food scarcity.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Rarámuri religious traditions involve ceremonies intended to heal what they refer to as "illnesses of the soul" as well as physical ailments. However, there is no evidence that these practices were part of an institutional system of care for the elderly or the infirm.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Learning took place informally through storytelling, engagement in rituals, and hands-on training guided by shamans (owirúame) or respected community figures. (Levi, 1999)

Reference: Levi, J.M.. "Hidden Transcripts Among the Rarámuri: Culture, Resistance, and Interethnic Relations in Northern Mexico". *American Ethnologist* 26, no. 1 (1999): 90-113.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Current ritual leadership is situational and rotating; there are no formalized religious administrative or bureaucratic structures within the group (Levi, 1999). Little is known about social and political structures before Spanish arrival.

Reference: Levi, J.M.. "Hidden Transcripts Among the Rarámuri: Culture, Resistance, and Interethnic Relations in Northern Mexico". *American Ethnologist* 26, no. 1 (1999): 90-113.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: In current Rarámuri settlements each household is responsible for the cultivation, harvesting, and storage of its own maize. It is common for families or "rancherías" (small rural settlements) to engage in systems of mutual aid, sharing resources to ensure greater diversity and food security within the community. (Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017) Little is known about cultivation structures before Spanish arrival.

Reference: Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017.
<https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-aramuri>.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– El campo lo desconoce

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Punishments for individuals who committed offenses against the community were believed to be administered by the gods themselves, who would inflict illness upon the offender, their family, or their crops. It was also held that through the use of the peyote scrape, known as "Jikuri sepawa'ame," souls were purified and transgressions cleansed. (Velasco Rivero, 1983)

Reference: Velasco Rivero, P.. Danzar O Morir: Religión Y Resistencia a La Dominación En La Cultura Tarahumara. México: CRT, 1983.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Although the Rarámuri are known to be fast runners and skilled hunters using bows and arrows, there is no evidence indicating that they had a formal military structure or organized warrior groups. (Lieberman et al., 2020)

Reference: Lieberman, D. E., M. Mahaffey, S.C. Quimare, N.B. Holowka, I.J. Wallace, and A.L. Baggish. "Running in Tarahumara (rarámuri) Culture: Persistence Hunting, Footracing, Dancing, Work, and the Fallacy of the Athletic Savage". *Current Anthropology* 61, no. 3 (2020): 356-79.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Notes: Before the Spanish conquest, the Rarámuri did not use a writing system. Knowledge was passed down orally through stories, rituals, and symbolic practices. Lumholtz's early twentieth century work argued that their language was only transcribed during the colonial period by missionaries using the Latin alphabet. (1902) Recent research echoes these arguments. (López Austin and López Luján, 2020; Martínez Ramírez, 2020)

Reference: López Austin, A., and L. López Luján. *El Pasado Indígena*. México: FCE, 2001.

Reference: Martínez Ramírez, M.I.. *Teoría Etnográfica: Crónica Sobre La Antropología Rarámuri*. Mexico: Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, 2020.

Reference: Lumholtz, C.. *Unknown Mexico; a Record of Five Years' Exploration Among the Tribes of the Western Sierra Madre; in the Tierra Caliente of Tepic and Jalisco; and Among the Tarascos of Michoacan*. United States : C. Scribner's sons, 1902.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

— No

Notes: There is no confirmed evidence of a formal calendar in traditional Rarámuri religion. However, linguistic and historical analyses of the 1683 *Compendio del Arte de la Lengua de los Tarahumares y Guazapares* suggests that counting and timekeeping held cultural significance. This implies they may have had a sophisticated way of tracking days or cycles, even if no formal calendar structure has been identified. (Rodríguez López, 2010; 2023)

Reference: Rodríguez López, A., ed.. *Gramática Tarahumara (1683): Compendio Del Arte De La Lengua De Los Tarahumares Y Guazapares De Tomás De Guadalajara*. Edited by A. Rodríguez López. Chihuahua: Universidad Autónoma de Ciudad Juárez, 2010.

Reference: Rodríguez López, A.. "Sobre El Trabajo Perdido Del Compendio De La Lengua De Los Tarahumares Y Guazapares De 1683". *Anales De Lingüística*, no. 10 (2023): 15-44.

Reference: Rodríguez López, A.. "Un Aporte De La Etnohistoria a La Etnomatemática Rarámuri (tarahumara)". *Memoria Americana: Cuadernos De Etnohistoria* 31, no. 1 (2023): 45-68.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Sí

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

–Caza (incluyendo animales marinos)

–Agricultura a pequeña escala/jardines horticolas o huertos

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Rarámuri, Kennedy, J. G.. "Tesguino Complex: The Role of Beer in Tarahumara Culture". *American Anthropologist* 65, no. 3 (1963): 620-40.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017. <https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-raramuri>.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Wyndham , F. S.. "The Semiotics of Powerful Places: Rock Art and Landscape Relations in the Sierra Tarahumara, Mexico.". *Journal of Anthropological Research* 67, no. 3 (2011): 387-420.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Pintado Cortina, A.P.. *Tarahumaras*. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004.

Reference: The Rarámuri, González, L.. *Crónicas De La Sierra Tarahumara*. México: SEP, 1987.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Zingg, R.. *Behind the Mexican Mountains*. Edited by H. Campbell, J. Peterson, and D. Carmichael. United States of America: University of Texas Press, 2001.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Bonfiglioli, C., and A. Gutiérrez del Ángel. "Peyote, Enfermedad Y Regeneración De La Vida Entre Huicholes Y Tarahumaras". *Cuicuilco* 19, no. 53 (2012): 196-222.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Fujigaki Lares, J. A.. *La Muerte Y Sus Metáforas: Ensayo Sobre La Ritualidad Mortuoria Y Sacrificial Rarámuri En El Noroeste De México*. Tesis de Maestría. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2009.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Merrill, W. L.. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Ronquillo Arvizu, Martín. "La Centralidad Del Kórima Entre Los Rarámuri. Un Recorrido De Su Tratamiento Teórico Etnográfico.". *Diario De Campo*, no. 2 (2018): 77-99.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Fujigaki Lares, A.. "Camino Rarámuri Para Sostener O Acabar El Mundo. Teoría Etnográfica, Cambio Climático Y Antropoceno". *Laboratorios De Historia Indígena Contemporánea*, 2020, 1-35.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Martínez, I.. "Sueños Y Chamanismo Rarámuri: La Generación Y El Control Del Conflicto Social". In *Iniciaciones, Trances, Sueños. Investigaciones Sobre El Chamanismo En México*, 251-66. Mexico: Plaza y Valdés México, 2010.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Bennet, W.C., and R.M. Zingg. *The Tarahumara, an Indian Tribe of Northern Mexico*. Univ. Chicago Press, 1935.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Bonfiglioli, C.. "Jikuri Sepawa'ame (la " Raspa De Peyote"): Una Danza De Curación En La Sierra Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 39, no. 2 (2005): 151-88.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Bonfiglioli, C.. "El Yúmari, Clave De Acceso a La Cosmología Rarámuri". *Cuicuilco* 15, no. 42 (2008): 45-60.

Reference: The Rarámuri, de la Cerda Silva, R. , and F. Gómez González. "Rarámuri: Mi Diario Tarahumara". *Revista Mexicana De Sociología* 10, no. 3 (1948): 433-34.

- Reference: The Rarámuri, Lumholtz, C.. Unknown Mexico; a Record of Five Years' Exploration Among the Tribes of the Western Sierra Madre; in the Tierra Caliente of Tepic and Jalisco; and Among the Tarascos of Michoacan. United States : C. Scribner's sons, 1902.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Velasco Rivero, P.. Danzar O Morir: Religión Y Resistencia a La Dominación En La Cultura Tarahumara. México: CRT, 1983.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Cajas Castro, J.. La Sierra Tarahumara O Los Desvelos De La Modernidad En México. México: Consejo Nacional para la Cultura y las Artes, 1992.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Fried, J.. "The Relation of Ideal Norms to Actual Behavior in Tarahumara Society". *Southwestern Journal of Anthropology* 9, no. 3 (1953): 286-95.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Montemayor, C.. Los Tarahumaras: Pueblo De Estrellas Y Barrancas. Mexico: Editorial Aldus, 2008.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Sariego Rodríguez, J.L.. El Indigenismo En La Tarahumara: Identidad, Comunidad, Relaciones Interétnicas Y Desarrollo. México: Instituto Nacional Indigenista. INAH, 2015.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Acuña Delgado, Á.. "Correr Para Vivir: El Dilema Rarámuri". *Desacatos*, no. 12 (2003): 130-46.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Ortega, R.. Relaciones Interétnicas En La Sierra Tarahumara: El Caso De Munérachi, Batopilas.. Mexico: Tesis de Licenciatura. Escuela Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Unidad Chihuahua, 2010.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Acuña Delgado, Á.. "Análisis Estructural Y Valor De La Resistencia En La Carrera Rarámuri De La Sierra Tarahumara.". *Dimensión Antropológica*, no. 27 (2003): 105-38.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Mancera-Valencia, F. J.. Patrimonio Biocultural De Chihuahua. México: Consejo Nacional para la Cultura y las Artes-CONACULTA, 2015.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Martínez, I.. "Tejiendo Como Caminos La Vida Social: Teoría Rarámuri De La Sociedad Y La Persona". In *Hilando Al Norte. Nudos, Redes, Vestidos, Textiles*, 555-62. México: COLSAN-COLEF, 2012.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Garrido, J.P.. Danza Y Contexto: El Pascol Rarámuri En La Baja Tarahumara. Tesis de Maestría. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2011.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Garrido, J.P.. Sistema Ritual-festivo En La Barranca Tarahumara El Caso De Guadalupe Coronado. México: Tesis de Licenciatura. ENAH, 2006.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Arvizu Castillo, T.. Relatos Tarahumaras. Kí'á Ra'ichaala Rarámuli. México: Consejo Nacional para la Cultura y las Artes / Dirección General de Culturas Populares-CONACULTA, 2002.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Instituto de los Pueblos Indígenas de Mexico, ed.. "Atlas De Los Pueblos Indígenas De Mexico - Tarahumaras". Edited by Instituto de los Pueblos Indígenas de Mexico, 2020. <https://atlas.inpi.gob.mx/tarahumaras-ubicacion/>.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Rodríguez López, A.. "Religión O Praxis Religiosa En El Mundo Indígena: El Caso Rarámuri Del Alto Río Conchos". *Cuicuilco* 19, no. 55 (2012): 43-68.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, López Austin, A., and L. López Luján. *El Pasado Indígena*. México: FCE, 2001.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Martínez Ramírez, M.I.. *Teoría Etnográfica: Crónica Sobre La Antropología Rarámuri*.. México: Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, 2020.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Lukacs, J.R.. Doctoral Dissertation Research: Burial Caves of the Sierra Tarahumara: A Multidisciplinary Study with Implications for the Greater Southwest.. United States: University of Oregon, 2003.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Chacón Soria, E.. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Breen Murray, W.. "Tres Sitios De Pinturas Rupestres En La Alta Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 20, no. 1 (1983).
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Lieberman, D. E., M. Mahaffey, S.C. Quimare, N.B. Holowka, I.J. Wallace, and A.L. Baggish. "Running in Tarahumara (rarámuri) Culture: Persistence Hunting, Footracing, Dancing, Work, and the Fallacy of the Athletic Savage". *Current Anthropology* 61, no. 3 (2020): 356-79.
- Reference: The Rarámuri, Lomnitz-Adler, C.. *Exits from the Labyrinth: Culture and Ideology in the Mexican*

National Space. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Levi, J.M.. "Hidden Transcripts Among the Rarámuri: Culture, Resistance, and Interethnic Relations in Northern Mexico". *American Ethnologist* 26, no. 1 (1999): 90-113.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Bye, R.A.. *Ethnoecology of the Tarahumara of Chihuahua, Mexico*. United States: Harvard University Press, 1979.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Arrieta, O.. "Religion and Ritual Among the Tarahumara Indians of Northern Mexico: Maintenance of Cultural Autonomy Through Resistance and Transformation of Colonizing Symbols". *Wičazo Ša Review* 8, no. 2 (1992): 11-23.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Acuña Delgado, É.. "Semana Santa En Norogachi: Fiesta Y Espectáculo Del Sincretismo Religioso Rarámuri". *INDIANA*, no. 22 (2005): 101-26.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Levi, J.M.. "The Embodiment of a Working Identity: Power and Process in Rarámuri Ritual Healing". *American Indian Culture and Research Journal* 23, no. 3 (1999): 91-114.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Rodríguez López, A.. "Un Aporte De La Etnohistoria a La Etnomatemática Rarámuri (tarahumara)". *Memoria Americana: Cuadernos De Etnohistoria* 31, no. 1 (2023): 45-68.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Rodríguez López, A., ed.. *Gramática Tarahumara (1683): Compendio Del Arte De La Lengua De Los Tarahumares Y Guazapares De Tomás De Guadalajara*. Edited by A. Rodríguez López. Chihuahua: Universidad Autónoma de Ciudad Juárez, 2010.

Reference: The Rarámuri, Rodríguez López, A.. "Sobre El Trabajo Perdido Del Compendio De La Lengua De Los Tarahumares Y Guazapares De 1683". *Anales De Lingüística*, no. 10 (2023): 15-44.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Sí, López Austin, A., and L. López Luján. *El Pasado Indígena*. México: FCE, 2001. ,

Reference: *El campo lo desconoce*, Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, ed.. "Etnografía Del Pueblo Tarahumara (rarámuri)". Edited by Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2017. <https://www.gob.mx/inpi/articulos/etnografia-del-pueblo-tarahumara-raramuri>. , , , , ,

Reference: Sí, Wyndham , F. S.. "The Semiotics of Powerful Places: Rock Art and Landscape Relations in the Sierra Tarahumara, Mexico.". *Journal of Anthropological Research* 67, no. 3 (2011): 387-420.

Reference: No, Pintado Cortina, A.P.. *Tarahumaras*. México: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2004. , , , , ,

Reference: *El campo lo desconoce*, González, L.. *Crónicas De La Sierra Tarahumara*. México: SEP, 1987. ,

Reference: Sí, Zingg, R.. *Behind the Mexican Mountains*. Edited by H. Campbell, J. Peterson, and D. Carmichael. United States of America: University of Texas Press, 2001.

Reference: Sí, Bonfiglioli, C., and A. Gutiérrez del Ángel. "Peyote, Enfermedad Y Regeneración De La Vida Entre Huicholes Y Tarahumaras". *Cuiculco* 19, no. 53 (2012): 196-222. , ,

Reference: Sí (especifique): *Clothes, corn, beans, personal objects.*, Fujigaki Lares, J. A.. *La Muerte Y Sus Metáforas: Ensayo Sobre La Ritualidad Mortuoria Y Sacrificial Rarámuri En El Noroeste De México*. Tesis de Maestría. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2009. , ,

Reference: Sí, Merrill, W. L.. *Rarámuri Souls: Knowledge and Social Process in Northern Mexico*. United States: Smithsonian Institution Press, 1988. , , , , , , , , , , ,

Reference: Sí (especifique): Onorúame (Supreme god) communicates with the living in a symbolic and indirect way—through signs in nature, dreams, rituals, and the mediation of shamans (owirúames). (Martínez, 2010), Martínez, I.. "Sueños Y Chamanismo Rarámuri: La Generación Y El Control Del Conflicto Social". In *Iniciaciones, Trances, Sueños. Investigaciones Sobre El Chamanismo En México*, 251-66. Mexico: Plaza y Valdés México, 2010. ,

Reference: Sí (especifique): The owirúames are the "shamans" responsible for healing and leading rituals, serving as a connection between Rarámuri society and the gods. (Bennet and Zingg, 1935), Bennet, W.C., and R.M. Zingg. *The Tarahumara, an Indian Tribe of Northern Mexico*. Univ. Chicago Press, 1935. , ,

Reference: Sí, Bonfiglioli, C.. "Jíkuri Sepawa'ame (la " Raspa De Peyote)": Una Danza De Curación En La Sierra Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 39, no. 2 (2005): 151-88. ,

Reference: Yes, Bonfiglioli, C.. "El Yúmari, Clave De Acceso a La Cosmología Rarámuri". *Cuiculco* 15, no. 42 (2008): 45-60.

Reference: No, Lumholtz, C.. *Unknown Mexico; a Record of Five Years' Exploration Among the Tribes of the Western Sierra Madre; in the Tierra Caliente of Tepic and Jalisco; and Among the Tarascos of Michoacan.* United States : C. Scribner's sons, 1902. ,

Reference: No, Velasco Rivero, P.. *Danzar O Morir: Religión Y Resistencia a La Dominación En La Cultura Tarahumara.* México: CRT, 1983.

Reference: Sí, Montemayor, C.. *Los Tarahumaras: Pueblo De Estrellas Y Barrancas.* Mexico: Editorial Aldus, 2008.

Reference: No, Rodríguez López, A.. "Religión O Praxis Religiosa En El Mundo Indígena: El Caso Rarámuri Del Alto Río Conchos". *Cuicuilco* 19, no. 55 (2012): 43-68. , ,

Reference: *El campo lo desconoce*, Martínez Ramírez, M.I.. *Teoría Etnográfica: Crónica Sobre La Antropología Rarámuri.* Mexico: Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, 2020. , ,

Reference: Sí (especifique): Caves., Chacón Soria, E.. "La Muerte En El Mundo Tarahumara". *Arqueología Mexicana* 29, no. 175 (2022): 34-39. , , , ,

Reference: Sí, Breen Murray, W.. "Tres Sitios De Pinturas Rupestres En La Alta Tarahumara". *Anales De Antropología* 20, no. 1 (1983).

Reference: No, Lieberman, D. E., M. Mahaffey, S.C. Quimare, N.B. Holowka, I.J. Wallace, and A.L. Baggish. "Running in Tarahumara (rarámuri) Culture: Persistence Hunting, Footracing, Dancing, Work, and the Fallacy of the Athletic Savage". *Current Anthropology* 61, no. 3 (2020): 356-79. , ,

Reference: *El campo lo desconoce*, Lomnitz-Adler, C.. *Exits from the Labyrinth: Culture and Ideology in the Mexican National Space.* Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992. ,

Reference: *El campo lo desconoce*, Levi, J.M.. "Hidden Transcripts Among the Rarámuri: Culture, Resistance, and Interethnic Relations in Northern Mexico". *American Ethnologist* 26, no. 1 (1999): 90-113. ,

Reference: Sí, Bye, R.A.. *Ethnoecology of the Tarahumara of Chihuahua, Mexico.* United States: Harvard University Press, 1979.

Reference: Sí, Arrieta, O.. "Religion and Ritual Among the Tarahumara Indians of Northern Mexico: Maintenance of Cultural Autonomy Through Resistance and Transformation of Colonizing Symbols". *Wičazo Ša Review* 8, no. 2 (1992): 11-23.

Reference: *El campo lo desconoce*, Acuña Delgado, É.. "Semana Santa En Norogachi: Fiesta Y Espectáculo Del Sincretismo Religioso Rarámuri". *INDIANA*, no. 22 (2005): 101-26.

Reference: Sí, Levi, J.M.. "The Embodiment of a Working Identity: Power and Process in Rarámuri Ritual Healing". *American Indian Culture and Research Journal* 23, no. 3 (1999): 91-114.

Reference: No, Rodríguez López, A.. "Un Aporte De La Etnohistoria a La Etnomatemática Rarámuri (tarahumara)". *Memoria Americana: Cuadernos De Etnohistoria* 31, no. 1 (2023): 45-68.

Reference: No, Rodríguez López, A., ed.. *Gramática Tarahumara (1683): Compendio Del Arte De La Lengua De Los Tarahumares Y Guazapares De Tomás De Guadalajara.* Edited by A. Rodríguez López. Chihuahua: Universidad Autónoma de Ciudad Juárez, 2010.

Reference: No, Rodríguez López, A.. "Sobre El Trabajo Perdido Del Compendio De La Lengua De Los Tarahumares Y Guazapares De 1683". *Anales De Lingüística*, no. 10 (2023): 15-44.